

Effectiveness the Training Certification of In-Service Teacher on The Improvement of Competency Profile of Social Studies Teacher

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Abstract. This research is carried out from the fact that the competency profile of social study teachers has not been optimal despite they have taken the teacher certification training. There is a gap between the training participant which tend to obtain a welfare improvement and the government expectation which expect to the teacher profile competency improvement. The research objective is to conduct a deep analysis related to the effectiveness of the Teacher Competency Learning and Training (PLPG) implementation to the competency profile of social studies teacher. The quantitative approach with a survey method is carried out in this study while the study design is grouped to the descriptive and verification study. The data is analyzed using Structural Equation Model (SEM) analysis. The Population and sample are 95 social studies teachers who have taken the certification training in the district 134 University of Pasundan Bandung in 2012. The result of the descriptive analysis shows that the learning process in the teacher certification training has low effectiveness influence to the profile competency of social studies teacher. The instructor is suggested to stress the andragogy learning concept in the learning process to achieve the training goal effectively. Therefore, it is also suggested to perform a training implementation result evaluation to be a feedback for the next training implementation.

Keywords: Teacher's Certification Training, Competency Profiles of Social Studies Teachers

I. INTRODUCTION

The position and role of teachers in providing education in schools and the implementation of learning in the classroom is very strategic in improving the quality of education [1]. The role of teachers as well as implementing changes to the implementing learning at grade level are expected to be realized in accordance with the implementation requirements specified learning [2]. As noted [3] that, "*teachers are the dominant factors being the input in the transformational process of education at schools*", which means that the teacher is one of the dominant factors that serve as inputs in the process of transforming education in schools. Poulou also noted that the component has been great affecting the educational process is a component of teacher [4].

Teachers have a key role in education because everything was prepared in good education facilities, fees, curriculum, learners and the management system of education would be meaningless if they are not given a touch of professionalism by teachers or will be of low quality if teachers are not professional [5]. This is in line with that proposed by [6] that:

Nearly all current Efforts reform-defining outcomes and standards, strengthening curriculum, using more powerful teaching and learning practices, redesigning assessment, changing decision-making structures-depend to some degree on the knowledge and capabilities of teachers. Unless teachers are Able to use high-quality materials and more effective strategies, UNLESS they can hold students to higher performance standards, schools will continue as they are. We must have teachers who are fully professional.

But in fact, there are many teachers in Indonesia at this time that still can not be said to be a professional. This phenomenon is visible from the unpreparedness of teachers by the time they require to be certified that they can demonstrate their competence. Another phenomenon that indicates the weakness of the professionalism of teachers in Indonesia is the gap between the ideal level in the Act and the realities facing education today. First, almost half of the approximately 2.78 million teachers in Indonesia do not have sufficient competence to teach. Insufficient qualifications and competence to teach in schools. This is confirmed by [7] that:

Statistics from the Ministry of National Education (MONE, 2008) indicate that teachers in Indonesia have a relatively lower level of academic qualification than Reviews those in neighboring nations. More than 60 percent of the total 2.78 million teachers have not reached the level of academic qualification of a four-year bachelor's degree (S1 / D4). In this group of teachers, the majority have either a D2 (two-year diploma) or a senior secondary qualification certificate. Most teachers from this group (about 70 percent) teach in the primary schools.

Data from the Ministry of Education shows that more than 65 percent of the total of 2.78 teachers in Indonesia does not meet the requirements for teaching. That condition shows that the quality of teachers in Indonesia still is low.

The high and low quality of education are also seen from the high and low quality of teachers [8]. The existence of adequate infrastructure may not be able to improve the quality of education directly in the absence of high-quality teachers [9]. Efforts to improve the welfare of teachers, are rated better to be able to improve the quality rather than through the provision of infrastructure alone [10]. Therefore, in order to realize improved quality and welfare of teachers, the government issued Regulation of the Minister of National Education of the Republic of Indonesia Number 18 the year 2007 on Teachers Certification enhanced by Minister of Education and Culture No. 5 of 2012 on Teachers Certification; and on July 13, 2007 published decision of the Minister of National Education No. 057 / O / 2007 on the Establishment of Universities Operator Certification for Teachers, which is enhanced by the Minister of National Education Decree No. 022 / P / 2009 concerning Establishment of Universities Operator Certification for Teachers.

Empirically, based on the number of studies conducted by several researchers on the effects of teacher certification training to increase their competence, it was revealed that the training was good relative to increase the motivation, interest, competence, and performance of teachers [11]. However, several other studies have shown that teacher certification training is also not significantly improve the competency of teachers [12].

The government has conducted various efforts to improve education by taking a central increased professionalism, quality, and a number of teachers [13]. However, the results do not seem encouraging for their various of the implementation, and not involve the teachers in setting its policies [14]. As for the government's efforts to improve knowledge, teaching skills and welfare for teachers, among others: (1) improve their knowledge and teaching

skills, the government has sought through various upgrading/teacher training and improving the qualifications of teachers from various levels to S1; and (2) improve the welfare of teachers by increasing salaries and provide functional benefits even several regions provide support incentives for teachers, introduced a system of assessment credit number of teachers for promotion and so teachers over two years can be promoted / class, impose competency testing and certification teachers, and provide professional allowance for teachers who have passed the certification through the portfolio as well as through the Education and training professional teachers (PLPG) for those who did not pass the portfolio.

The results showed that the government's efforts seem to have a significant impact on improving the quality of education [15]. This was partly caused by (1) Various upgrading or teacher training has been less evaluated and monitored the implementation and impact to the bottom level; (2) In terms of teacher qualifications, lack of material deepening of curriculum subjects and a variety of science teacher training and assessment as well as writing Scientific Writing (KTI); (3) The increase in salary and functional allowance, is still not comparable with the basic tasks and functions of the teacher (who should), what more when compared with salaries or allowances of teachers in other countries; and (4) There are a lot of teachers teach subjects that are not in accordance with the educational background or discipline of science. Of the 267 participants of the training of teacher certification for Social Sciences in 2011 at the University of Pasundan Rayon 134, only 44 (16.48%) teachers have the educational background of Social Sciences remaining 223 people (83.52%) is not background Sciences social (Sergur Rayon 134 in 2011).

The phenomena described above indicate that many teachers of Social Sciences instead of the field of Social Sciences. This means that the competence of the teachers of Social Sciences is still relatively low [16]. Low competence, in turn, may result in low quality of teaching has resulted in the low quality of education [17].

To increase the competence and professionalism of teachers attempted through teacher certification, but the result of in-service teacher training certification is not yet satisfactory. This is demonstrated by the performance and ability of teachers of Social Sciences after PLPG that has not shown significant improvement. Based on interviews with teachers of Social Sciences who have followed PLPG, the teachers stated that what is obtained from PLPG short-lived. Furthermore, the lesson back to the old habits of origin or where the delivery of the subject matter in a conventional manner. The cause of the return of the habit of teachers in teaching Social Sciences in conventional learning how to be caused by several factors such as (1) The limited time for

studying with a variety of methods to explore the capabilities of the students as the target time must be pursued in accordance with the curriculum; (2) lack of ability of teachers in teaching students to be active students (*student centered*); and (3) How to study in PLPG less touch needs teacher professionalism.

Increased competence of teachers this can be done through education and training teacher certification [18]. Efforts were largely determined by the results of the training. The results of the training itself are determined by various factors implementation of education and training [19]. Various theories about the training that effectively has been often mentioned by experts, including from [20], [21] with the model CIRO, [22], [23], [24], [25] to [26] also [27], In essence, the training is effective consists of several sequential stages, starting from level 1 called the participants' reactions to the training program, level 2 with regard to the learning that is how much the changes in knowledge, skills and attitudes resulting from the implementation of the training, level 3 related with how much change the behavior of participants of the training in the workplace caused by training, level 4 relates to the result of that is what training benefits for companies that are caused by the training of the participants. Subsequent developments, [25], apply a level 5 which is the return on investment and return on that expectation, and level 6 suggested [26] is a broader contribution that the development potential of training participants in the long term. [27] basically a training program that is effective that: "(1) *Based on needs*, (2) *Aimed at objectives*, (3) *Scheduled at the right time*, (4) *Held at the right place*, (5) *For the right people*, (6) *conducted by an effective leader*, (7) *using effective techniques*, (8) *Objectives are Reached*, (9) *Participants are satisfied*, and (10) *the program is evaluated*". It has previously been described by Noe et al. (2000: 210-201) that the framework is an effective training program "Refers to a systematic approach for developing training programs, that presents the six steps of this process: (1) conducting needs assessment, (2) ensuring the employee's readiness for training, (3) creating a learning environment, (4) ensuring the transfer of training, (5) selecting training methods, and (6) evaluating training programs."

Based on the results of previous research and theoretical frameworks that is exist regarding the training of the teaching profession, the study of the factors that affect training certification of teachers towards improving the competence of teachers of Social Sciences to conduct an empirical study on participants PLPG Teachers Certification 2012 in Rayon 134, very important to do.

B. THEORETICAL

1. Training results

The results of this training are very related to the evaluation of learning training program [28]. Assessment of the results of the training program can assist in the evaluation with regard to the effectiveness of the training program. These results should be related to the goals of training programs, which help training participants understand the purpose of this program [29].

Referring to the opinion [30], evaluation of training results at least can be grouped into three categories: cognitive outcomes (*cognitive outcomes*), psychomotor outcomes (*skills-based outcomes*), and affective outcomes (*affective outcomes*). Cognitive outcomes are used to determine the level of understanding of the training participants about the principles, concepts, facts, technique, or process that is given to the education and training programs so that the participants' knowledge can be measured by using the results of the test [31] (formative evaluation and summative, results of pretest and posttest, or initial competency test scores and grades multiple-choice written test / essay).

The results are used to assess the level of psychomotor skills or motor skills and behavior [32]. The results include the acquisition or psychomotor learning skills and apply these skills in the workplace (skill transfer) [33]. Achievement of these skills can be evaluated by observing the performance of teachers as participants of the training through simulation teaching practice (*peer teaching*) [34]. In the simulation teaching practice, instructors and other training participants to make observations, comments, and assistance when needed.

Affective outcomes include attitudes and motivation [35]. One type of affective outcomes is the training participants' reactions to the training program. This reaction refers to the perception and level of satisfaction of training participants to the training program as a whole, which includes infrastructure training, instructor competency, training material, etc. [36]. This information is generally obtained at the end of the training session. Reaction helpful training participants to identify satisfaction and achievement of training participants also identify factors that impede learning training participants [37]. Networking the information can be collected through a questionnaire that asked about the level of motivation of the participants in following the training or the satisfaction level of participants to the training program, the ability of the instructor in one session, the learning method, the comfort of the study, the adequacy of accommodation, service training committee, and so on.

2. Teacher Competence Social Studies

Implementation of learning social studies in junior high is demanding an understanding, competence and high

performance of teachers [38]. The success of social studies teachers in carrying out their duties is not only reflected in the results of learning but also determined through a process of creative learning and innovative learning process effectively Social Studies.

In Law No. 14 of 2005 on Teachers and Lecturers (article 1, paragraph 1), explained that "Teachers are professional educators with the primary task of educating, teaching, guiding, directing, train, assess and evaluate students on early childhood education, formal education, education elementary and secondary education ". In line with its main task, the teacher is implementing changes at once implementer of learning at grade level. Teachers are the critical success factors of a learning process in achieving the goals set.

Teachers as professional educators, according to [39] demonstrated by the performance of the following five:

- a. the desire to always display the standard approach ideal behavior;
- b. improve and maintain the image of the profession;
- c. the desire to always pursue professional development opportunities to enhance and improve the quality of knowledge and skills;
- d. the pursuit of quality and ideals of the profession; and
- e. pride in his profession. [40]

Teachers as professionals need to be able to show their best performance. By [41] Lecturer (Article 4), "the role of the teacher as a learning agent serves to improve the quality of national education", can present the best learning services in producing graduates who meet the public expectation.

A professional teacher is required to implement the national education system and achieve national education goals, namely the development potential of students through service learning allows learners are able and willing to learn, feel welcome to learn, resulting in the development of potential in accordance with expectations of the learning process and results.

[41] (Article 7), explaining the teaching profession as a special area of work carried out by the following principles:

- a. have talent, enthusiasm, spirit and idealism call,
- b. is committed to improving the quality of education, faith, piety and noble character,
- c. have academic qualifications and educational background in accordance with its duties,
- d. have the necessary competence in accordance with its duties,
- e. has responsibility for the execution of tasks professionalism,

- f. earn income determined in accordance with work performance,
- g. have the opportunity to develop in a sustainable manner with the professionalism of lifelong learning;
- h. have legal protection in carrying out the task of professionalism, and
- i. have a professional organization that has the authority to regulate matters relating to the duties of professionalism of teachers.

Such principles should be a reference for teachers to be able to present a service-learning is effective in achieving a goal. In line with the effectiveness of the learning process, [42] in the National Seminar-Teacher Certification Professional Education and Prospect LPTK, explains the basic tasks of teachers as follows:

- a. Helps learners to develop their full potential so that grow and develop with total and complete;
- b. help learners to the potential intellectual, emotional, social and spiritual grow in a balanced and harmonious and perfect;
- c. transform a variety of knowledge to the learners using the approach and methodology of creativity in the teaching-learning process, so that science and knowledge and creativity of learners grow and develop;
- d. instill basic values are positive and necessary in life into learners so attached and grew to become one with the behavior of learners;
- e. build character and personality of students to be people who have the character and personality intact and perfect;
- f. helped develop the ability of learners in its function as a social being civilized and dignified;
- g. foster within students the values of good behavior, and
- h. provides guidance for learners to know where the good works and what does not, which prohibited where some are not prohibited, where the act is wrong and which is also true that need to be in a life full of peace, tranquility, and harmony.

In line with the basic tasks of teachers, [43] (Article 1) explains that "each teacher shall meet the standards of academic qualifications and competence of teachers nationally applicable". Ownership certificate and certificate of competence by a teacher are expected to reflect professionalism in performing basic tasks and development.

Fulfillment standard academic qualifications and competence of teachers, coaching, and development can be done with reference to:

- a. Standard academic qualifications of teachers,
 - 1) "Provided through higher education degree program or diploma program four" [44]; Article 9.
 - 2) "The teacher at SMK / MAK or other forms equivalent must have a minimum education qualification of

Diploma (D-IV) or equivalent (S1) study program in accordance with the subject taught / of teaching, and was obtained from an accredited institution" (Appendix [45]).

Qualification of teachers should be reflected in the program in accordance with the subjects of teaching and was obtained from an accredited institution.

- 3) The standard of teacher competence include; "Pedagogical competence, personal competence, social competence, and professional competence acquired through professional education" [44], Article 10, paragraph 1), is the basic capabilities possessed a professional teacher, to be further developed in order to carry out its role in accordance with the demands learning services.

Association of Institutions of Higher Education Personnel Indonesia (ALPTKI) makes operationalize the basic competence of teachers into the following formula [42]:

Pedagogical competence is the ability to manage the learning of students, which include; 1) understanding of learners, 2) design and implementation of learning, 3) evaluation of learning and 4) the development of learners to actualize various potentials. Professional competence is the ability in mastering the learning material is broad and deep that enable guiding learners to meet the standards of competence. Competence mastery personality is steady, stable, mature, wise and authoritative, become role models for students, and noble. Social competence is the ability to communicate effectively with students, fellow educators / other education personnel, parents/representatives of students, and the surrounding community.

Coaching and development of basic competence of teachers should be aligned with the subjects of teaching or interested by the teacher concerned. In addition, cultivation and development of basic competencies that teachers refer to the strategic factors of human life are expected to produce teachers capable accordance with the development needs of education services in general and education of students in particular.

Appendix [45] on Standards of Academic Qualifications and Competencies Teachers include details of the teacher competency standards subjects at every level of education. At least, teachers should have the competence of teachers in mastering the characteristics of learners, plan learning in the classroom, managing the learning process in the classroom, conduct an assessment of learning outcomes in the classroom, utilizing information and communication technology for the sake of learning, deliver or provide the subject matter, adjust the material to the needs of students,

involved in teacher professional development reflectively, following the change in the learning environment, utilizing information and communication technology, demonstrated work ethic and responsibility, being, to uphold the code of ethics of the teaching profession, an example for the students and the community, acting objectively, interact with friends peers, interact with parents of learners, seeks to involve external parties in the learning program, to adapt to the school environment, and are involved in the implementation of the program in improving the quality of education.

[46] about the contents of the standard states that "social studies learning, learners can be directed to Indonesian citizens of a democratic and responsible, as well as citizens of the world who love peace". The contents of the above-mentioned Permendiknas own purposes in everyday life in the community, in accordance with the Decree of the Minister of educational objectives, set out in [47]. Furthermore, with reference to the Permendiknas, a social studies teacher must have the ability:

- a. introducing concepts that relate to people and the environment;
- b. have the basic ability to think logically and critically, curiosity, inquiry, problem-solving, and social skills in life;
- c. commitment and awareness of social values and humanity; and
- d. have the ability to communicate, cooperate and compete in a pluralistic society, locally, nationally, and globally.

Competence social studies teacher at this must refer to meaningful learning, integrated, value-based, challenging, and active, as stated [48] that "*Teaching and learning in social studies are powerful when they are meaningful, integrative, value-based, challenging, and active* ", all of which should lead to the pedagogical, personality, social, and professional. In this study, measurement of teacher competence SOCIAL STUDIES refers to the competence profile of teachers, namely competence (1) pedagogical, (2) personality, (3) social, and (4) professional.

II. METHOD

Based on the characteristics of the variables studied, this study was conducted using a survey method [49], which is a method used to reveal the facts of a phenomenon in the field so it can be evaluated based on the reviews the theoretical, as well as various studies conducted previously, to then be withdrawn became an inference about the influence of the components of the training, the training results and their impact on raising the profile of teacher competence Social Sciences junior who follow the training of the teaching profession in 2012 at Rayon 134 (Pasundan University, Bandung).

The study design is divided into two parts, namely descriptive and verification. Descriptive method is to provide an overview of the various characteristics of the variables studied the form of the training and raising the profile of teacher competence Social Sciences. Verification method used to describe the relationship of causality (causal) between the variables under study [50].

The population in this study are all teachers of Social Sciences of the Department of Education who participated in training on PLPG Teacher Certification in 2012 at Rayon 134, totaling 97 people, who came from 85 schools (79 junior and 6 SMK) in six regencies/cities in West Java. List of training participants and their institutions of origin can be found in the appendix. In this study, all the teachers as respondents. This means that the sample is saturated samples. Data is returned and can be processed is as much as 95 respondents. Two respondents did not return the instrument as it was out of the teaching profession. Teachers who serve this population only training participants on PLPG Teacher Certification in 2012. The reason for choosing the population of participants in 2012 was different from previous years, namely that the certification system in 2012 has adopted the form of workshops and training courses prior to attending training in teacher certification 2012 participants were required to follow the Initial Competency Test (UKA).

Necessary data in this study are primary data and secondary data. The primary data source for this study is the head of junior high school / vocational school teachers follow the training its Social Sciences at PLPG Teacher Certification in 2012 at Rayon 134 (University Pasundan) and 95 teachers who attended the training. The headmaster assesses teacher competence profile of Social Sciences. Secondary data relating to the value of a written test, the value of *peer teaching*, and the value of participation, which is obtained from the 2012 teacher certification committee for Rayon 134, used for training outcome variables. As enrichment, engineering interviews with principals and teachers are also planned to be performed.

1. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

2. Results Effectiveness Training to Increase Teacher Competency Profile Social Sciences

Results of testing hypotheses in the model influence the results of the training to improving the competency profile of teachers of Social Sciences shows that the results of the training do not have a significant effect on raising the profile of teacher competence Social Sciences. This can mean that the training results will not necessarily be able to raise the profile of teacher competence Social Sciences.

Training results directly positive effect but not a significant increase in teacher competence profile of Social Sciences. This means that empirically the effect of the results of training on teacher competency profiles for Social Sciences insignificant. In other words, the results of the training participants Professional Teacher Education and Training for Teachers Certification 2012 in Rayon 134 can not increase the competence profile of teachers of Social Sciences significantly. Conditions that shows that teachers who get high scores on the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective, do not automatically profile competence is high, likewise, that teachers who get high scores on the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective, not automatically the profile of competence is low. Thus, the high-low profile of competence is not directly determined by the high and low results of training in scores on cognitive, psychomotor, and affective, but rather is determined by the impact of the implementation of the training itself, which consists of the analysis of training needs, the characteristics of the training participants, environment learning training, training and learning process. That condition shows that the reality is contrary to the principles of the functionalist theory proposed Parsons [51] that "Schools are competitive and the best students will go on to the best jobs whereas Weaker ones will have to take low pay and low-status work. Schools teach children that it is fair to have different rewards and so they teach children to be competitive ". This means that the form of education and training of teachers is also to be competitive so that teachers who excel and have gained a lot of training will get a job and a better position, while teachers are underachieving and lacking in a lot of training does not necessarily get a job and a better position. The principle of this functionalist theory of teachers because there is research from Berg [52] which showed that "better-educated workers are no more productive than those who are less educated, and in some cases even less productive".

Teacher certification program held by the Indonesian government since 2006, is one form of an acute qualification program. The program refers to the term Dore [52] is a "development impact late". On teacher certification program, educational certificates have become an imperative requirement for teachers to gain entry are securely fixed to be educators with no additional income in the form of certification allowances, in contrast to teachers who do not have a teaching certificate.

Teachers who obtain the benefits of certification are required to teach a minimum of 24 hours per week. The demands of teaching hours at least 24 hours per week, on the one hand led to an excess of teachers in certain subjects, such as the results of the analysis of the needs of educators conducted by the Directorate of basic education Kemendikbud RI in 2012 teacher of Social Sciences for junior high schools in Indonesia excess of 9999 teachers

, This condition is a consequence of the growth of credentialism or qualification. In connection with credentialism or qualification, [53] states that:

What Collins calls **credentialism** - the process whereby educational systems come to be built around the pursuit of educational certificates for occupational Reviews their value rather than around learning as valuable for its own sake - Dore Refers to by the term **qualifications**. He Suggests that it is a significant phenomenon in all or most major industrial societies. All (or at least most) contemporary nations have Tus Become infected with what Dore calls "**the diploma disease**." The diploma disease is a type of vicious circle in the which individuals Become obsessed with the acquisition of diplomas or degrees Because employers Increasingly emphasize such educational certificates in their statements of job qualifications. The two sides feed off each other, and educational certificates Inflate as a result.

Referring to the opinion [54] explained that there are two serious conditions that will occur as a result of growth qualification, ie there is excess teacher first and second decline in the quality of education. Deterioration in the quality of education characterized by routine importance curiosity and creativity. Similarly, in the activities of teacher certification, teachers are more concerned with passing the certification exam and immediately received a teaching certificate to be submitted soon to the government in order to receive benefits educator's certificate. In connection with their teaching competence, [55] stated that teachers who have passed the certification of competence taught him better than teachers who have not passed the certification of teachers. In connection with the motivation and performance of teachers, [56] suggests that the effect of certification to improve the motivation and performance of teachers.

The results of this study are also consistent with the results of the study [57] that there are two things that cause results not training can have a major impact on improving the quality of teachers: (1) Training is not based on real problems in the classroom (*unrealistic class problem*). Instructors deliver the same material to all teachers but they come from different areas and resources madrasah conditions vary. Almost all instructors are forgetting the principle of heterogeneity capabilities, facilities, access, and others in the region. In other words, the condition of the madrasah others not necessarily the same even though it is in an adjacent region; (2) the implementation of the results of training that is not yet fully. Results of a new training program at the level of knowledge, it is not applied in the classroom. This could be caused by *content* training material that is oriented so that the theory can not be applied or also in the absence of post-

training monitoring. Training only be considered as the ritual is complete without *follow-up* and coaching.

The influence of teacher certification on teacher performance disclosed [58] that the certification has been able to improve the welfare, dignity of teachers, discipline and pedagogical competence. Certification is not much altered the performance of a teacher: a) the newly received SK, has not dropped his support and b) who retire c), a teacher who has worked at the institute has been consistently making changes, or no certification, continue to occur both teachers are certified or not. Similarly, the opinion [59] that certification in junior high school teacher who studied in the West Java is a very low correlation to the increased professionalism and the quality of learning. However, in spite of that, the model proposed in this study indicate that the training results of the simultaneous influence on improving teacher competence profile of Social Sciences, although not significantly. The result of the training has a positive and significant impact on the improvement of teacher competence profile of Social Sciences, with a note that the results of the training path coefficients directly to the improvement of the competence profile is not significant.

2. Research findings

Findings from this study indicate that the training results do not significantly affect the increase of teacher competence profile of Social Sciences. The results of the training itself have not fully significantly improve teacher competence profile. Once analyzed, the conditions turned out to be sourced from the condition and motivation training participants who tend to only expect to receive the benefits of the teaching profession once they graduate training, without any attempt to raise the profile of competence.

The implications of the findings of this study indicate that the implementation of the training is in line with its impact, which is the result of Social Sciences teacher training, but the results of Social Sciences teacher training is not yet fully in line with the impact of increased teacher competence profile of Social Sciences. Based on these findings, it is necessary to evaluate the results of the training by the organizers. In addition, there needs continuous teacher development program post-training certification through a variety of other related training organized by schools, offices, and MGMPs.

III. CONCLUSION

Based on the formulation of the problem, the research hypothesis, the results of research and discussion, the conclusion that can be drawn is that this study are consistent with previous research that this study differs from previous research that states that there is influence the results of the training to improving the competence of teachers, because in this study found that the results training did not

significantly influence the improvement of teacher competence profile. In particular, the conclusions of the research results can be presented as follows: The results of the training directly no significant effect on raising the profile of teacher competence Social Sciences. This condition indicates that the training results are not yet fully in line with the impact of increased teacher competence profile of Social Sciences. This relates to the functionalist theory that did not go well. That is the hope the training participants with the government's expectations are not in line because students are more likely in increased welfare while the government expects an increase in the competence profile participants of the training with the addition of well-being.

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